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Evaluation of Distance Learning Practices (From the Instructors Perspective): Planning, Implementation and Evaluation

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Abstract

This research aims to examine distance education practices from the perspective of instructors in terms of Planning, implementation and evaluation. It is aimed to reveal the current situation regarding the planning, implementation and evaluation of distance education practices by ensuring that the distance education practices related to the teaching methods and techniques used in the courses, content and process are evaluated from the perspective of the instructors. The study group of the research consists of 20 instructors. In the research, qualitative data were obtained by the case study method. In the study, the data were collected using the semi-structured interview technique developed in consideration of the purpose of the research. Qualitative content analysis was used in the analysis of the data obtained. The results of the research reveal the positive and negative opinions of the instructors in terms of planning, implementation and evaluation. Considering the findings by institutions, practitioners, and the Council of Higher Education that implement distance education may contribute to increasing the quality of education.

Keywords: COVID-19 Pandemic, Distance Education, Planning, Implementing, Evaluation, Curriculum

1. Introduction

1.1 Introduce the Problem

With the gradual differentiation of societies and the rapid development of technology, there are also differences in the wishes and needs of individuals. The constant change of tools does not allow us to predict the situations we may encounter. Every change and differentiation requires individuals to adapt to the new world order.

Adapting to any change in societies is thanks to education (Akpınar, 2003). Educational systems are the economic, political, social and cultural basis of society. Education systems should be organized in a way that is open to developments and flexible, and the needs of individuals should be taken into consideration. The change of education systems and their renewal in line with the needs are very important in terms of creating qualified individuals who can realize themselves.

In this context, the aims of the higher education system are to train qualified individuals who will contribute to the scientific, technological, economic, cultural and social development of countries. Universities support and implement new student-centered methods, adapting to new lifestyles, social and lifelong learning in the new world order. With distance education, which has recently been implemented all over the world, the needs of individuals are tried to be met.

There are many studies in the world regarding the integration of technology into education (Goktas, Yildirim & Yildirim, 2008). One of these studies is the practicality of distance education. Factors such as the rapid proliferation of information technology, rapid access to information, and the practicing of many web designs to the educational environment have increased the practicality of distance education. Organizing, evaluating and using information is also important (Karahana & Izci, 2001). For this reason, it is inevitable to constantly develop new technological tools. Distance education enables individuals to benefit from educational opportunities from their environment without time and place restrictions. It is a form of education where the instructor and the learners are in different places, in a planned learning environment, using web tools. It is necessary to know how to organize learning and learning activities, which techniques, methods, materials, and how to adapt the content. In this context, it is seen that distance education needs specific theories. Independent work, autonomy, communication and interaction, cooperation, community, etc. This is taken into account when designing distance education. With distance education, education has become more individual, accessible and economical (Isman & Dabaj, 2005). Distance education is preferred because it has a flexible structure and information can be accessed 24/7.

The roles of teachers and students have also changed with distance education. The teacher has taken on the role of resource provider, guide, observer, communication reinforcer from the role of material distributor. While the student was a passive receiver, over time, s/he started to take place in the center of learning, became responsible for his/her own learning, producing, sharing, determining the content and communicating (Gokmen, Duman & Horzum, 2016). As a result of the literature review, it has been observed that distance education has become widespread in an increasing momentum and it has been observed that it will maintain its importance in the future (Aydin, 2020).

Not only technological developments, but also situations affecting countries may require the use of distance education in educational environments. Due to the Covid-19 pandemic that we are experiencing today, distance education has taken place rapidly in the world. Countries were caught unprepared for this transition, and there were discussions about the differences in opportunities among students (Ozer, 2020). Many scientists are of the opinion that the teaching converted to distance education in these emergency situations is not real distance education classrooms because instructional designs, content and assessment cannot be carried out within a well-planned/designed plan (Gardner, 2020).

In the literature review, the problems experienced in the planning/design of distance education, the implementation process and assessment and evaluation were compiled. According to the report prepared by Bonk (2001) for teaching staff, time problem in planning and developing distance education, lack of experience and training, technical/infrastructure problems and lack of technical support, lack of administrative support, motivation, lack of interest, pedagogical deficiency, cost, trust is in the form. Another problem experienced in distance education is that there is not face-to-face communication (Telli & Altun, 2020). In the research conducted, faculty members expressed similar views. Interaction and communication in distance education are the general problems encountered during the practicing.

According to Falowo (2007), teacher-student and student-student interaction are not sufficient, materials are not prepared in accordance with students, technology is not used efficiently, students do not show enough interest in distance education courses (Saritas & Barutcu, 2020). The other mentioned problems are that the programs are not suitable for distance education (Li, 2009; Zan & Zan 2020) and that effective methods are not used in the course design phase (Cronje, 2001; Zan & Zan 2020). The less active participation of students in the courses given by distance education is also supported by a study.

Regarding the problems encountered, the deficiencies are tried to be eliminated in the process and the structuring continues. It is also possible to enrich face-to-face education with distance education. The flipped classroom model, blended learning etc. which are used today, can be an example of these. In these models, the aim is to enrich the content, contribute to the effective learning of the students and to take an active role in learning.

The perspectives of the instructors are very important for the effective and efficient implementation of distance education practices in higher education (Dooley & Murphey, 2000). Considering the situations that motivate the instructors, it is said that making practicing with new teaching methods and techniques, technological adaptation, sharing knowledge, professional development (Green, Alejandro & Brown, 2009). In addition, the availability of support and guidance on financial and necessary practices is one of the most important factors (Moore & Anderson, 2003).

It has been concluded that distance education has as much effect as face-to-face education on student performance and interaction of instructors with distance education teaching experience (Ulmer, Watson & Derby, 2007). According to Lloyd, Byrne, and McCoy (2012), the situations that cause problems in distance education in general are low student participation, lack of feedback from students, lack of interaction, problems in preparing materials, inexperience, inaccessibility to the material and the course, increased workload, technical problems (as cited in Gurer, Tekinarsan & Yavuzalp, 2016).

When the literature was searched, many studies on distance education were found (Ozgol et al. 2017), but the studies on distance education, which started abruptly due to the recent pandemic, are still limited and new. Because the practicing is new and sudden, many problems may occur. This study is also important in terms of increasing the efficiency and quality of the practicing in distance education.

For these reasons, it is important to get the opinions of the instructors in terms of the practicality of the distance education practicing in universities. While this research is being conducted, the effects of the Covid-19 pandemic continue, and it is not known how long the process will last. For this reason, this study can be considered among the first studies conducted in Turkey regarding distance education in this period. This study will also shed light on future studies in terms of eliminating and strengthening the deficiencies of the distance education practices.

In this context, the problem statement of the research is; What are the opinions of the instructors on distance education practices?

2. Method

In this study, case study, one of the qualitative research approaches, was used. The case study is a research method in which the exact boundaries of the situations that occur in a certain time period are in a whole with their own context and it is difficult to draw and are examined in depth (Yin, 1984, Creswell 2007 cited in Yildirim & Simsek, 2013). The most distinctive feature of this method is to examine the person to be examined in its own context due to its unique characteristics (Yin, 1984). Case studies are based on the questions of "what," "how" and "why" and allow a detailed examination of a phenomenon or event that the researcher cannot control (Yildirim & Simsek, 2013). Situations are limited by time and events, and extensive data is collected and analyzed in depth using various data collection methods. With the holistic multi-state design, there is more than one situation that can be perceived as holistic on its own. Each situation is handled holistically in itself and then compared with each other (Yildirim & Simsek, 2013). For these reasons, the purpose of the research is not to

generalize on the universe, but to understand and explain the distinctive features of the person, community or situation. With these results, case study is seen as an appropriate method for this research to achieve its purpose.

2.1 Participant Characteristics

The data of this research was carried out with 20 instructors working at Mersin University in 2020, carrying out distance education activities. The selection of the participants was based on ensuring maximum diversity. The aim of maximum diversity is to create a small sample and reflect the diversity of individuals to the maximum extent (Yildirim & Simsek, 2013). 8 of the instructors are women and 12 are men. The ages of the instructors vary between 30-49. Their academic experience varies between 2 and 25 years, and their academic levels are Master's and Doctorate. 15 of the instructors did not participate in any course/activity related to distance education and 13 of them did not give any distance education before the Covid-19 outbreak. Instructors conduct distance education courses simultaneously or mixed (Table 1).

Table 1: Characteristics of the Instructors Participating in the Interview

Participants		
Characteristics	Number	Frequency
Gender		
Man	12	60
Woman	8	40
Total	20	100
Age		
30-35	11	55
36-40	7	35
41 and above	2	10
Total	20	100
Education Level		
Master	4	20
Doctorate	16	80
Total	20	100
Title		
Dr. Research Assistant	2	10
Instructor	7	35
Dr. Instructor	4	20
Asst. Prof.	5	25
Assoc. Prof.	2	10
Total	20	100
Academic Experience		
1 - 5 years/years	10	50
6-10 years	3	15
11-15 years	6	30
15 years and above	1	5
Total	20	100

2.3 Data Collection Tool

When the literature is examined, there are various types of interviews and they are generally grouped under 3 categories. These; structured, semi-structured and unstructured (Merriam, 2009). In this study, data were collected by semi-structured interview technique. With this method, previously determined interview questions were asked to the instructors in the determined order, and new questions were added according to the progress of the interview in order to get more in-depth and detailed information in line with the answers from the instructors (Merriam, 2009).

Interviews were conducted over the web-based video conference system with the "Instructor Interview Form" created for the purpose. An appointment was made before the interview from the instructors selected for the interview.

These are the questions that the researchers themselves produced as a result of the literature review while creating the interview form. In line with the purpose of the study, the main themes of the interview questions were determined as planning, implementation and evaluation. The prepared questions were examined by 5 field experts (2 experts in the field of distance education), necessary changes were made on the questions and they were finalized. During the data collection process, an average of 20 minutes with each participant. The ongoing conversations were recorded electronically and converted into written form.

2.4. Validity and Reliability

In order to increase the validity of the research, the interview questions prepared were evaluated by 5 researchers who were experts in the subject before they were applied, and they were applied after the necessary improvements were made according to the suggestions made. Another title that was forgotten to be added to the academic level section was added, corrections were made in punctuation marks, and some words that created confusion were removed. Some questions are divided into two because they are long. In order to increase the reliability in the analysis of the data, the codes were checked by different researchers and a code list was created by reaching a consensus.

2.4.1. Research Ethics

The data in the study were collected on a voluntary basis. Instructors were reminded that they could terminate the research process at any time. In addition, no information that would disclose the identity of the participants was included. In addition, since the research is not an applied study, it does not have a dimension that will negatively affect the participants physically or psychologically.

2.5. Analysis of Data

Content analysis technique was used in the analysis of the data obtained from the interview forms. The basic process in content analysis is to gather similar data within the framework of certain concepts and themes, and to interpret them by arranging them in a way that the reader can understand (Yildirim & Simsek, 2013, p. 259). In content analysis, the stages of coding and categorizing the data, finding the themes, organizing and defining the data according to the codes and themes, and interpreting the findings follow each other (Yildirim & Simsek, 2013).

In the analysis of the data obtained, the process started with the transcription of the interview records. Themes were created by grouping codes from the ideas given by each instructor to a question, sub-themes from these codes with similar content, and sub-themes with similar content. Tables showing the codes, sub-themes and themes for each question in the interview forms were arranged and a coding table was created. Each participant was given a letter before analyzing the data.

Two researchers coded the data separately using the coding table. At the end of this process, 90% coding compatibility was achieved (Miles & Huberman, 1994). The reliability formula ($\text{Reliability} = \frac{\text{Consensus}}{\text{Agreement} + \text{Disagreement}} \times 100$) suggested by Miles and Huberman (1994) was used to calculate the reliability of the study. By discussing the non-common codes, the inter-research agreement was increased to 100%. Afterwards, all of the data were coded by a researcher and the process continued. In addition, "direct quotations," which is another reliability criterion, are included.

3. Results

The findings regarding the planning/design, implementation process and measurement and evaluation parts of distance education practices are evaluated under the categories as in Tables 2, 3 and 4.

Table 2: Codes, Sub-Categories and Frequency Table Created in Terms of Design/Planning

Themes and Subthemes	Codes	Frequency	
A. EXPERIENCE			
a. Experience-Aim	Planning	5	
	Target Audience Needs	6	
	Compliance With The Electronic System	4	
	Benefitting Different Sources	3	
	Few Topics	2	
	b. Experience -Content	Being Functional	4
		c. Experience-Learning Experiences	Communication
	Interaction		5
	Trust		2
	Keeping the Student Active		8
Intelligibility	7		
Fun and Eye-Catching Material	4		
Using Case Studies	3		
d. Experience -Evaluation Approaches	Information		5
	Process evaluation	4	
B. PROBLEMS			
	Motivation	4	
	Material preparation	4	
	Relapse	4	
C. SUGGESTIONS			
	Providing Active Participation	9	
	Focusing	6	
	Motivation	3	
	Prepare A Guide	2	
	Careful Planning	4	
	Interesting Material	5	
	Designing Functional Content	3	
	Ensuring Equal Opportunity	4	
	Suitability For Target	7	

As seen in Table 2, how are the views/evaluations of the instructors regarding the design/planning of the distance education practices of the research? In line with the answers and coding given by the participants to their questions, sub-themes were formed under the experiences, problems and suggestions and the frequencies related to them were included.

Codes related to experiences were created over the elements of the curriculum. It was mentioned that the experience of the instructors was analyzed in terms of the target, and the needs of the target audience, the achievements and the content of the program were taken into account while planning. The necessity of preparing a guide in accordance with the electronic system and the use of different sources were mentioned, and the planning of the content with a few subjects in order not to lose the focus of the student and to ensure permanence was mentioned. Below are examples of the answers given by the instructors.

Planning: *“First of all, it is necessary to make a planning for each lesson. In other words, what are the behavioral changes of students week by week, first of all, the gains need to be determined. Since the content comes to us ready-made from YOK, the knowledge, skills and attitudes that we want to see in students actually come ready-made. We plan our lessons accordingly. ...Moreover, I design and prepare a course material in my mind within the framework of the content that I have to present, considering the knowledge, skills and attitudes that I want to see from the student within the framework of the course” (F).*

“To begin with, I helped students to form an academic and professional knowledge about the course by making explanations about the course, what their achievements, experience and professional knowledge will be” (B).

“I stick to the curriculum more in terms of the preparation process. First of all, my limitation is the curriculum” (S).

Target audience needs: *“...it is important to be able to determine what the student wants” (L).*

Compliance with the electronic system: *“We are trying to bring the materials into a format suitable for the online system” (R).*

“I adjusted my course materials according to the distance education format” (T).

Benefitting different sources: *“In order to make the trainings more understandable, care should be taken to use slides, videos, materials and other sources as much as possible” (B).*

“... I suggested to students the main sources to be used, reference sources if any, and intellectual sources that they can follow depending on their personal preferences” (Y).

Few topics: *“When planning, it is important to have few topics, it is necessary to ensure the permanence of the knowledge without tiring the student” (M).*

In distance education, I always advocate that few subjects are presented to students in an efficient way. I'm trying to do the same myself. Trying to teach many subjects to students can be tiring for both students and us (C).

“Do not engage in exaggerated curriculum loads, it is not efficient anyway” (B).

It was mentioned that the content should be suitable for daily life/functional, case studies, and fun and attention-grabbing in order to ensure the permanence and focus of the student. Regarding the practicing part, the importance of communication, interaction, trust in the instructor, trying to keep the student active in the process, making the content understandable and supporting with examples were emphasized. Below are examples of the answers given by the instructors.

Being Functional: “It is necessary to give examples from life and human resources issues that will arouse curiosity in students” (F).

“...it is necessary to give practical lessons” (F)

Fun and eye catching material: *“While preparing the material, it is necessary to use video-supported materials with plenty of visuals that will enable the participation of the student. Because we cannot ensure participation or we lose focus very quickly” (M).*

“If there are videos that I can use online, I try to use them. If not, I go to the lab and shoot a video myself. For the sake of adding visuality” (N).

“... I try to present interesting presentations by adding visuals” (E)

Using case studies: *“I prepare presentations and case studies. I am definitely preparing two case studies on each subject. After explaining the subject, I am talking about these case studies. And I present them separately to the students” (R)*

“... while explaining the subject as much as possible, I say that you can write about the case studies if there is something that happened to them. Somehow I want someone to post a note there on the message board. I try to include such students as much as possible” (F).

Regarding planning in distance education before the practicing, the instructors emphasized the importance of communication, interaction, clarity and trust, and stated that they kept the course duration short in order to keep the students active. Below are examples of the answers given by the instructors.

Interaction: *“Adding more interactive videos, uploading more attractive teaching materials, using different interactive and different platforms that appeal to more sense organs and are suitable for their development levels will motivate them” (F).*

“However, I believe that it is more beneficial to teach interactive lessons rather than a monotonous instructor. Thus, you can keep the distracted attention on the lesson all the time” (A)

Trust: *“The biggest disadvantage of distance education is social isolation, so it is very important for students/trainees to trust the trainer” (A).*

Keeping the student active: *“It is important to involve the student in this process” (F).*

"We try to keep students in class by preparing quizzes, quizzes, forum discussion questions" (T).

"In order to keep the student active, we have shortened the lesson times (T).

"Since it is not like face-to-face training, I think that the lessons should not be more than half an hour in order not to decrease the efficiency" (B).

Intelligibility: "We are trying to prevent problems in both expression and perception in the online system" (R).

Regarding assessment and evaluation, it was stated that they informed the student from the beginning of the process and they made a plan to evaluate the process. Below are examples of the answers given by the instructors.

Process evaluation: "We removed our midterm week, instead of quizzes, our forum discussion questions, homework project etc. we prepare, spread the process over 14 weeks, average at least 7 quizzes, forums, etc. We determined it to be" (T).

"Can I make a process-based assessment or on which subjects should I specifically take an exam? I definitely determine beforehand" (F).

"I have preparations in the form of a quiz in 3-4 weeks. On behalf of whether they understand the lesson or not" (S).

Information: "At this stage, I gave detailed information about the system to the students, both verbally in the course and in written form over the system, both in exams and in homework" (B).

"I always informed the student beforehand during the exam process; I have clearly informed the students about the subjects and resources that the student will be held responsible for in the exams. I have always tried to make a fair scoring and assessment and evaluation according to the level of the students" (Y).

"I warn students from the beginning about copying. I state that I want them to be original" (E).

Another theme that emerged in the planning phase of distance education is on problems. Instructors stated that both they and the student experienced a loss of motivation from the beginning of the process. They stated that the loss of motivation caused them to fall into repetition while planning the lessons, they had difficulty in preparing materials in accordance with the online system and they wanted to receive support in this regard. Since they cannot see the body language of the students, the instructors, who do not know whether the student participates actively or not, are worried about whether the lessons will be understandable even at the planning stage. Below are examples of the answers given by the instructors.

Repetition, loss of intrinsic motivation: "The courses I conducted were generally management courses, in this sense, there were presentations I gave in the course, PowerPoint presentations. I used to update them every year, frankly, distance education killed my desire to renew myself. For the first time, I am teaching the previous year's course without renewing my career" (F).

"I can say that there is a loss of motivation of both students and instructors" (H).

"Students have very low motivation in the lessons. I see that they are not prepared enough or not willingly for the assignments and presentations I have given before. (P).

Material preparation: "Preparing materials suitable for the distance education system can be tiring. Sometimes I realize that I am repetitive. Trying to support continuous motivation or thinking about active participation is exhausting. Materials should be effective and support should be provided for systemic situations" (P).

"The biggest problem is in preparing material. In distance education, the teaching materials we prepare can be mostly in the form of preparing ppt presentations. But I know that these are not effective and efficient. These trainings should be given on more interactive platforms. We may not have enough technological knowledge or time" (F).

"I had problems in preparing and uploading material systematically. I solved them by converting them to other formats" (T).

"Some lessons need equipment to be taught/designed, but if you can get them yourself, you can get them or not if you don't. I would not have been able to do the accounting course without the tablet pen my wife bought for her own institution. I wouldn't be able to do it efficiently. There are lessons to be told on the slide, there are lessons that cannot be told. Institutional support is important. We bought the camera and microphone ourselves. We also choose which program we will tell. These are the big obstacles in planning" (O).

As a suggestion, they mentioned that in order to ensure active participation, focus and motivation of the students, they should plan well, use interesting materials and share content suitable for daily life, ensure equality of opportunity, and plan with assessment and evaluation in accordance with the target, and thus the practices will be more accurate and effective. and made recommendations.

To actively participate: *".... to be able to teach fluently and sustainably in front of the screen, to keep the student's attention in the lesson and to make it possible to participate in the lessons, etc. I can recommend them to take them into account and if they believe that they have deficiencies, they should correct these deficiencies"* (Y).

It is interesting and useful in daily life: *"Human resources issues that will arouse curiosity in students, examples from life should be given"* (F).

"It is important to enrich the content visually. After all, laboratory lessons were the lessons that the students came and studied, they should be more interactive, the student should attend the lesson" (N).

"I make it interesting for them by including up-to-date information on every subject and techniques, not just relying on books, I recommend it" (P).

"Since it is not face-to-face, they will grab whatever they see in the visual, it is necessary for the materials to be interesting so that they are not too distracted" (E).

Guide preparation: *"The process of determining the goals and achievements of the course, and generally the course planning process takes place very quickly, but this is an experimentation process. Sample guides should be prepared for each course code"* (A).

Careful planning: *"I prepare my 14-week plan before the semesters begin, and I determine my presentations and textbooks accordingly. I prepared the same way in distance education, I had data and resources, good planning is important"* (H).

"When we come together with students synchronously, we need to spend our time productively. We need to make a plan regarding the practicing of the theoretical knowledge we want to give when it is asynchronous, and when we are synchronous, we also transfer the subject in the courses we conduct synchronously, as a suggestion, they should focus on the practicing in the synchronous courses" (F).

"The subject selection specific to distance education should be made. If the subject that will normally be taught in the classroom in 14 weeks includes 6 units, it should be halved in distance education. You have to choose the most important ones. It is necessary to choose the subjects that need to be focused on, it is necessary to explain few things well" (O).

Ensuring equal opportunity: *"All students who are subject to formal education in Turkey should have the same equal conditions. When this doesn't happen, it reduces our productivity for distance education, both for us and for the students."*

Suitability for target: *"It's important to be careful to ask questions that parallel what we taught about"* (H).

Table 3: Codes, Sub-Categories and Frequency Table Created in Terms of Practicing

Themes and Subthemes	Codes	Frequency
A. EXPERIENCE		
Experience- Method/Technic/Material	Appropriate Material (Video, Lecture Notes, Presentations, Case Study, Article)	9
	Relative To The Student	4
	Visuality	6
	Involving The Student In The Process	6
	Interaction	5
	Daily Topics	4
	Motivation	4
	Permanence	3
B. PROBLEMS		
	Infrastructure	9
	Interaction	4

Crowded classroom	3
Classroom Management	5
Inability To Focus	3
Participation	11
Course Access	5
Student Perception	2
Applied Lessons	2
Intelligibility	5
C. SUGGESTIONS	
Careful Preparation	5
To Adapt	4
Lesson Planning	5
Interesting	7
Visuality	9
Not To Repeat	4
Ensuring Participation	10
Technical Infrastructure	12
Preparing For The Hybrid System	2
Be Original	3
Transferability	3

What are the opinions/evaluations of the instructors regarding the distance education implementing process, which is the second sub-problem? In line with the answers and coding given by the participants to their questions, sub-themes were formed under the experiences, problems and suggestions, and the frequencies related to these were included (Table 3).

Experiences were evaluated as methods, techniques and materials. Regarding the implementation process, the instructors mentioned that the appropriate materials should be presented to the students in an appropriate way, including the planning phase of the course, and they mentioned that distance education provides flexibility in time and space, thus increasing the possibilities of sustainability and repetition. They also stated the importance of the student being involved and active in the process. The activeness of the student can also be ensured by the content and motivation presented in accordance with them. In addition, the instructors also underlined that permanence can be achieved in distance education by learning the content that is presented appropriately after providing the necessary motivation. Below are examples of the answers given by the instructors.

Appropriate material (video, lecture notes, presentations, case study, article): *"I upload my weekly materials to the system. I am also uploading all my resources. In order for my students to benefit easily" (T),*

"I have prepared personal lesson documents that mainly use animations and visual effects. From time to time, I made students watch videos that could be related to their lessons" (Y).

"...I use channels on the internet. I give the lecture notes to the students as pdf by adding videos to them" (N).

"I give articles to students every week in my graduate classes. We are examining these. I also take notes from 4 or 5 different sources for my undergraduate students. I give them to students" (H).

"...I share my own notes from the system and I tell the students live, we teach the things that we cannot express verbally through videos, and we teach our lessons in mutual communication" (S).

"I use different methods for different courses. For the course that students choose according to their own fields, I mostly use articles and techniques that can develop this area of interest. By finding compilations of different articles and discussing them with the students, I try to advance them by sending them all before the lesson, reading and discussing them and taking the floor in turn" (P).

"PowerPoint presentations, Word and pdf documents, I share. I try to use online platforms from time to time. I do screen shares" (F).

Relative to the student: *"I believe that it would be beneficial to develop the teaching methods according to the student's profile and capacity and turn them into a variable structure" (B).*

Visuality: *".... just sticking to the book also bores the students a little more, I support them with shapes and graphics" (T).*

Permanence: *"I never used ready-made resources, I prepared all the course materials myself. Thus, the lessons were handled much more authentically and their retention in mind increased"* (Y)

"I took care to describe the subjects and explain them in a way that would attract the attention of the students. I think that educators should develop and apply examples and methods of expression that will be permanent in the minds of students with their originality and intellectual background in the transfer process" (B).

When it is looked at the problems encountered in the implementation phase of distance education, it is mentioned that the interaction is not sufficient and the participation is low due to the high number of students in the classrooms. The high number of students in the classrooms also brings problems in classroom management. It is seen that the perception of the students also affects the instructors negatively. Instructors also mentioned that they encountered technical/infrastructure problems and that adequate solutions were not produced. They also complained that they could not receive sufficient systematic support in distance education.

Technical Infrastructure: *"Sometimes I see things that need to be run through one system split up over many systems. We teach the course on another platform, and we enter the grade announcements on a completely different platform"* (A).

"There were great difficulties in the transition period to the first distance education. We were almost doing distance education via chat. So we were writing. In the next period, this was exceeded a little more" (R).

"We may experience interruptions when the internet is sometimes heavily loaded" (D).

"Distance education is a difficult process, we are constantly checking whether my voice is sounding or not, these are major setbacks" (N).

"There may be connection problems. Sometimes there are audio and video problems. Infrastructure should be created very well, there should be a consultancy unit that provides 24/7 consultancy. There is such a system, but we cannot always reach it when we want. Most of the time I could not reach at all" (F).

"I am having problems with the infrastructure of the university. Internet disconnection during class. Insufficient infrastructure of platforms used by universities. The crash of the system you are going to teach at once. We couldn't log into the system for 2-3 weeks anyway. Sometimes you start classes late, sometimes you don't start at all. These also hinder your lesson planning" (O).

"If there is a mathematical expression on the board, I have difficulty in writing and conveying it, but I tried to solve this problem with writable tablets" (N).

Interaction: *"There is almost no student-instructor communication outside of the classroom. This is the biggest problem."* (A).

"There is no dialogue, we are constantly teaching monologue with the student, and this monologue gets really tiring after a while" (K).

"The efficiency in face-to-face education and distance education is not the same. There is very little interaction, there is no mutual conversation and dialogue, when one of them speaks, the other has to wait. Sounds intermingle" (S).

"The lessons become one-sided monologues. Therefore, it is necessary to keep the course duration short, to reduce the course content as much as possible, to share the materials by mentioning what the important parts are while teaching in the course, and to ensure that the students stay relevant to the subject" (O).

Crowded classroom: *"The materials in distance education are not very effective because it is too crowded. Normally, we can conduct the lesson with more participation in face-to-face education"* (G).

Classroom management: *"The crowded classrooms gave me great difficulties in managing the distance education process. Sometimes I can't even get an answer to a simple question in 75-person classes"* (G).

Inability to focus: *"You can teach in the classroom for 2 hours without a break, the student has to listen at that moment, but it is very difficult to listen to the lecture on the computer. A lot of separate lessons and separate motivation are not possible during the day"* (O)

Participation: *It has been stated by the instructors that the students' perceptions about distance education think that "we can pass the lessons anyway, there is no need to attend the lesson, it is not compulsory anyway, it is recorded and then I watch it." For these reasons, the result is that the attendance to the courses is low.*

"The biggest problem is that the student does not attend the lesson. The nature of distance education cannot force anyone to participate, it is against the nature of distance education. Participation is always good for the student, for this reason, the student should be motivated very well, by uploading more interactive videos, more attractive teaching materials, appealing to more sense organs, using different interactive platforms suitable for their development level, teaching the lessons in a life-oriented and practical way. will motivate them" (F).

“The biggest problem is the participation of the students in the course, the other biggest problem we experience is that the students see distance education very differently from face-to-face education, and the biggest reason for this is the privileges given to the students. For example, there is a feeling that there is no obligation to attend or you cannot give a low grade to the student” (R)

“The biggest problem is that we can't take attendance. The student does not show interest in the lesson, or rather, he does not attend the lesson at all. For example, I have students who have not come to my class since the semester started, and there are students who do not come to my class and do not listen to the registered lessons” (R).

“We don't know if the student is listening or not, we can't see if the program is open or not. We don't know if he was concentrating on it at that moment. There are various restrictions, he does not have to open his camera. He doesn't have to turn on his microphone. This reduces the trainer's motivation. Not so in the classroom. We could understand whether the student understood or not from their attitudes and actions. By telling it over and over, we were actually developing something specific to the person, but unfortunately that is not the case here” (S).

“Not being able to get feedback from students, instead of asking general questions to students, it is necessary to address students by their names and ask questions. Students are reluctant to participate or I direct instant surveys like “Do you agree with this” (T).

“Since the students are not obliged to attend, it negatively affects the perceptions of the students towards the course, and the students should be made to apply the attendance obligation” (H).

“It is a great loss of motivation to see 2-3 students in a class of 80 people. Therefore, it may not go as you planned... It is a big problem that students have unlimited absenteeism rights” (O).

Access to the course: *“Sir, I live in the village, I don't have a phone, teacher, I don't have internet excuses need to be removed... Students state that they have difficulty in accessing the classes” (H).*

“We have students who have difficulties in accessing the courses, and for them, we have already recorded the courses and uploaded them to the system. This is how we can solve this problem” (P).

Applied lessons: *“Students graduating from applied sciences can practice in the greenhouse in the field. From time to time, the laboratory can also do this, when these people do not see these practices, it is one-to-one. No matter how much we support it from afar, the person will have trouble in that regard because he does not do it himself. He needs to know how to plant, etc. I also have students who will work in the hospital. He should blend the basic information in practice so that he does not have a problem in business life” (S).*

Clarity: *“You can see from the eyes that the student understands you, you understand from the body language, but this is very difficult in distance education. It is very difficult to get feedback” (E).*

“Since we couldn't get any reaction from the students, you can't determine how much of what we said has reached... It is very difficult to get feedback from the students” (O).

According to the research, the majority of the instructors state that they have difficulties in technological support and the software used, and that the students do not participate sufficiently. Instructors need more technical support and training. They also emphasized the importance of the effectiveness of the program used.

Instructors generally suggested the situations they used in practice to other practitioners. To prepare carefully, to adapt to distance education and to plan the upcoming lessons accordingly, to use interesting and visually appealing materials, not to fall into repetition and to be open to innovation, to use new situations to ensure the participation of students, to be able to solve technical infrastructure problems, to be original and They made suggestions such as presenting functional studies. Below are examples of the answers given by the instructors.

Technical infrastructure: *“Universities need to develop their online education bases, and it will be beneficial to give the necessary training to the instructors about online education and material preparation” (R).*

“Universities need to be constructive within the scope of technological infrastructure, material support, seriousness in education and content protection” (O).

Originality: *“I find it important that the people who will give the training try to be original and always try to research new techniques, especially to apply methods according to the needs of the target audience” (Y).*

Interesting: *“Students need to prepare content in a way that grabs their attention and keeps their attention, and they really need to talk about topics that are relevant to their needs” (D)*

“I don't think the distance education system is that bad. Although we talked about the negatives in general. I think it will be useful when applied in an integrated way. I think it takes time. Both for us and for the students. It is important to use it effectively. It is important to find solutions to the negative aspects. I think better results will emerge when educational scientists work on these issues” (S).

“Ppt presentation, these have remained traditional now. Different interactive platforms should be used”. (F)

To Adapt: *“We couldn't fully adapt because we thought we would get through this process, but the trend shows that even if the pandemic is over, a certain percentage of the lessons can take place online. The age demands it” (R).*

“I suggest that whatever we pay attention to in formal education, we should do the same. People must have the ability to motivate themselves... They must be motivated” (H).

Transferability: *“We need to share information that will be useful to the student and transfer them to their lives” (F).*

It has emerged as a result of the answers given that the instructors consider face-to-face education more efficient than online education. It can be thought that this situation is due to the fact that the practice was carried out for the first time and the instructors generally did not have any previous distance education experience.

While looking at the problems of distance education in general, it is seen that the reasons such as the problematic technical infrastructure, insufficient participation and interaction, and intelligibility come to the fore. While looking at the solutions to the problems in general with the implementation process, it was seen that the majority of the instructors agreed with the suggestions that the technical infrastructure should be developed, the facilities should be made more professional and the expectations of the students should be taken into account. Based on this situation, it can be interpreted that the importance of considering the views of students and instructors while completing the infrastructure works is emphasized.

Table 4: Codes, sub-categories and frequency table created in terms of Measurement and Evaluation

Themes and Subthemes	Codes	Frequency
A. EXPERIENCE		
Experience- Types of Measurement and Evaluation	Open-Ended Question	10
	Multiple Choice	9
	Homework	6
B. Problems		
	Unable To Take Exam	5
	Technical Infrastructure	7
	Copy/Plagiarism	8
	Crowded Classes	6
C. Suggestions		
	Encourage Students To Think	4
	Education	2
	Measuring Method/ Rubric	2
	To Be Objective	4
	Do Not Force The Student	5
	Process Evaluation	8
	Open-Ended Question	7

As seen in Table 4, what are the opinions/evaluations of the instructors regarding measurement and evaluation in the distance education practices of the research? In line with the answers and coding given by the participants to the questions, sub-themes were formed under the experiences, problems and suggestions and the frequencies related to them were included.

When the coding of the Assessment Types/Experiences section is examined, the instructors stated that they can better measure the students and avoid the problems in the coding under the problems title, instead of taking online exams in general, they apply Open-ended questions, multiple-choice asynchronous exams with case studies, and give homework. Below are examples of the answers given by the instructors.

“I ask weekly discussion questions and short answer questions. I created a question bank, randomly selected different questions for each student on the same topic basis. In this way, I was able to avoid copying” (T).

“I tried to apply assessment and evaluation in the exam, which usually consists of open-ended questions, from time to time by giving homework in addition to the exam” (B).

“Even though I take care to ensure a fair, consistent and reliable result in the design of assignments and exams given in the assessment and evaluation process, I think that this situation cannot be balanced from time to time as a natural consequence of distance education. For this reason, I paid attention to the design of exams where original and personal interpretation is at the forefront so that assessment and evaluation can be healthier” (B).

“I generally preferred to have assignments, presentations and exams with few questions. The most important measurement and evaluation criterion for me was to see whether the student had a good command of all the subjects that I explained and conveyed to the student throughout the term” (Y).

“Homework, I can measure with written material, I ask both information and interpretation questions. I also ask interpretation questions that they can blend with knowledge” (H).

“Quiz and reports replace visas in applied courses, they are in the form of homework as a final, and homework must be submitted in 3-4 hours. It can also vary according to the course, in some courses this period can be increased to 1 week or we want a presentation” (N).

“I want them to make a presentation, in terms of individuality” (S).

“I prefer to give homework more” (E).

“From the beginning of the semester, I had a 1-2 question homework prepared after each lesson, and I developed such a scoring system by adding the scores out of 5 or 10 on these assignments on top of their visas. I plan to make an evaluation by adding other notes on top of it” (P).

“I don't do process evaluation. Since we haven't seen it, the participation is very low anyway. Since the participation is low, it becomes impossible to make an evaluation in the process. We have to evaluate the results. I give homework to students during the midterm and final semesters, the homework focuses on a topic, students focus on a single topic and copy each other and send it to me. Other topics are ignored. I focus on the assignment that students need to know most in practice. Including several knowledge and skills. At least, I prefer them to prepare an assignment that they can research and add something from themselves. At least they try to study a few subjects and use their creativity to prepare something” (F).

“Assignments and presentations are the techniques I use mostly. In this way, I prevented students from memorizing only to take the exam, and I was measuring the students' ability to question and produce solutions related to the lessons (Y)”.

“Even though I take care to ensure a fair, consistent and reliable result in the design of assignments and exams given in the assessment and evaluation process, I think that this situation cannot be balanced from time to time as a natural consequence of distance education. For this reason, I paid attention to the design of exams where original and personal interpretation is at the forefront so that assessment and evaluation can be healthier” (B).

When we look at the problems related to the measurement and evaluation part, when we look at the methods and techniques mentioned about the measurement and evaluation of the instructors, the instructors do not take the exams because online students have difficulties in accessing the exams, they cannot do it, and this process is given to the students by various techniques during the term, giving homework, making presentations, etc. It was concluded that they were subjected to process evaluation. Some teachers also stated that they had difficulty in reading the comment questions in crowded classrooms. Also, it seems that the biggest problem is cheating, plagiarism. Below are examples of the answers given by the instructors.

Technique/Infrastructure: *“I have to give homework because the infrastructure of the university is not suitable for online exams” (F)*

“We have been subjected to the betrayal of technology in the exams we have made, we are improving our system” (T).

“Our assessment and evaluation experience is not very productive, actually, our systems oblige us to either give homework or take an exam” (H)

“There are systemic problems. Students upload their assignments to the system and we grade them. We always have to write them down on paper. It needs to become more systematic. When I press somewhere, I need to get their document. These are always a waste of time. It is very difficult to write it down one by one and transfer it to the student information system” (F).

“We give them the opportunity to write by hand while taking the exams, so that the student who does not have a computer can write by hand while taking the test” (F)

Copying/Plagiarism: *“The distance education process is a system in which it is difficult to prevent preparation and copying activities, especially at the point of measurement and evaluation. For this reason, it seems like a more effective solution to prepare assignments and presentations specific to the course or subject, based on interpretation and encouraging research” (Y).*

“Students can gather in online groups and solve the same questions” (H).

“I ask questions about the opinions of the students in a way that they cannot find on the internet so that they do not send and copy to each other” (P).

“In order to avoid copying, I can do an open exam with everyone's camera” (S).

“You give 1 day, cheated again, 3 days again. You say you are disabled 40 min. You say let me pull the process. It also dissolves in groups collectively” (O).

“The distance education process is a system in which it is difficult to prevent preparation and copying activities, especially at the point of measurement and evaluation. For this reason, it seems like a more effective solution to prepare assignments and presentations specific to the course or subject, based on interpretation and encouraging research” (M).

Crowded classes: *“I have about 300 students and it takes a lot of time to read their homework” (G).*

“I have 110 students, I have to ask each student a comment question separately, this is how I can prevent cheating or plagiarism, which is a very challenging situation for a teacher”.

“We still have problems with measurement and evaluation. In other words, when we give an online education to a crowded classroom, we cannot perform the exam because some of the students state that they have great difficulties in accessing online education” (R).

“.... I am in favor of students making preparations rather than giving homework for a certain period of time. Students may have difficulties in accessing” (S).

Within the scope of measurement and evaluation, the suggestions of the instructors suggested that open-ended questions that would encourage students to think should be asked and thus copying should be prevented. It has been suggested that the assessment and evaluation method is important and that the rubric prepared should be more objective and fair on behalf of the students, that the prepared questions should be suitable for the target and that the student should be subject to the process evaluation. Due to the fact that the process is challenging enough, it was mentioned that it was unnecessary to force the student more and suggestions were made. Below are examples of the answers given by the instructors.

Encourage the student to think: *“Prepare multiple choice questions in a way that is thought-provoking and based on interpretation. If the exams do not focus on a single question pattern, they inevitably become a stimulus for the student and the student is encouraged to think” (A).*

“I recommend that students ask questions that can use their creativity. Asking questions in a way that the student can use his/her own originality rather than questions such as explain what is memorization and write it down” (O).

Assessment Method/Rubric: *“Instead of using the questions that already exist in digital media or printed works, I recommend that the instructor prepare his/her own questions and use a scale method consisting of specific details that can measure mastery of the course and the subject.” (Y).*

“They have to choose a measurement method according to the conditions of the university and they need to develop a measurement according to the structure of the course in order to make a healthy measurement” (F)

Objective: *“No matter which measurement and evaluation approach they apply; objectivity should be at the forefront.” (F).*

“In order for the assessment and evaluation system to be fair, consistent and reliable, it is necessary to prepare the questions in a more classical (open-ended) and original format in which personal interpretation is at the forefront” (B).

“I have always tried to give fair scoring and to measure and evaluate students according to their level. I didn't just subject the students to the exams they would take via remote access, I gave them assignments frequently and scored these assignments” (Y).

Not forcing the student: “The information you give in applied lessons may not go to the other side, we are the ones who feel this the most. We should not force the students in this process too much” (N).

Process evaluation: “This is necessary in terms of not sticking to a single exam and the functioning of the course. Even if face-to-face training is started, one should not stick to a single midterm exam (T).”

“Students can be given long periods of time for exams and homework. It should be a student-oriented system” (S).

“Presentations can be expected from each student at 2-3 week intervals. Of course, this is very difficult in crowded classrooms” (S).

“I wish we could evaluate the process, but it would be very challenging. It is important to inform the student at the beginning and say that they will be evaluated with tiny little notes and to create the appropriate process. But we have more bureaucratic procedures that make us more tired. These need to be minimized” (F).

Open-ended question: “If the exam cannot be done online and under good supervision, I plan to test the knowledge level of the student by asking interpretation-based questions, by asking open-ended questions that the person needs to answer specifically. If it is not done online, it should be done in this way” (P).

Education: “I do assessment and evaluation in the form of homework, which can cause me to evaluate the student sufficiently. If it is distance education, it is absolutely necessary to give practical training to the instructors, where we can make the multiple-choice exams more practical... I have multiple-choice tests with high validity and reliability. I also need to get an education on this subject. I don't know where and how to get it from whom” (F).

“Since I could not receive training on online systems, I already learned about my site by solving it by myself, but there is still an unfamiliarity with the system and I did not choose that system because I was concerned about determining the question styles for the online evaluation system” (P).

4. Discussion

With the sudden transition to distance education, it is in question that universities cannot adapt sufficiently. Distance education practices have affected both students and lecturers. Conducting the courses with purely technological tools can sometimes be challenging for both parties. According to Petzold (2020), the instructors who switched to distance education do not have sufficient pedagogical knowledge, and many of the instructors did not give distance education and did not give a seminar/course etc. related to distance education. they did not participate and this situation brings with it complexity for them (Bailey & Card, 2009). Trying to carry out distance education in the logic of face-to-face education is the main problem (Ozalkan, 2021). According to the findings of Tuncer and Tanas (2011) they concluded that most of the lecturers did not receive any training related to distance education. Considering the results of the research, the majority of the instructors stated that they did not have experience with distance education and did not receive any support. They think that this is due to the university they work at.

The most important opinion of the instructors participating in the research about the preparation and planning stages of the lesson is that they have the anxiety of teaching online. Instructors stated that they generally prepare for their lessons regularly and make their plans in advance. However, they mentioned that they had problems in being motivated to the lesson and that the students were not motivated enough, and that this situation had a negative effect on them while planning.

When some of the universities that provide distance education are examined, it has been observed that all of the materials opened for access are printed materials and there are no interactive resources (Can, 2020). For this reason, the materials to be prepared regarding distance education should be prepared in accordance with the distance education program and in a way that encourages student participation and motivation.

Tuncer and Tanas (2011) stated that there are problems in distance education due to teacher qualifications such as preparing quality materials, creating appropriate learning environments, communication and presentation in distance education. In the research conducted, they stated that there is usually no problem in preparing materials, and that they are more efficient in accessing resources. However, the majority of the instructors stated that they encountered technical problems. It has also been concluded that the practitioners who will provide distance education take a long time in the planning and adaptation stages of distance education, they lose control from time to time, they feel stressed at these stages, and they have difficulties in transforming the content they have prepared for face-to-face education in accordance with distance education practices (Marek, Chew & Wu, 2021). It has been concluded that most of the distance education instructors do not think of providing distance education after the pandemic period (Kurnaz & Sercemeli, 2020). (Erfidan, 2019) As stated by the instructors involved in the research on content, transferring the most important content to students is also supported by other studies (Sayan, 2020). Similar results were also obtained in the study.

When evaluated within the scope of measurement and evaluation, measurement and evaluation processes were suspended in many countries, and it was necessary to conduct online exams without validity and reliability studies instead of exams and tests (Bozkurt, 2020). In terms of assessment and evaluation, it was observed that students performed lower than face-to-face education (Falowo, 2007). When the students were asked how to do measurement and evaluation in distance education, it was concluded that they preferred homework and project studies (Zan & Zan 2020). Instead of face-to-face exams, homework that can be evaluated in the process, presentations to be prepared by students, etc. It has also been supported by the literature (Sayan, 2020). Instructors also shared similar views both in the planning phase and in the assessment and evaluation parts.

According to Baris and Cankaya, (2016), they stated that distance education provides rich content access, theoretical and verbal courses can be given more easily with distance education, but practical courses cannot be given. Again, in the same study, it was stated that there was no serious problem in reaching examples during distance education activities, and it was observed that the lecturers in the research expressed similar views.

According to the results of the research, there are still many problems in the implementation of distance education. It is possible to increase productivity by continuing distance education, improving the system, reviewing methods, awareness-raising and practices that will increase interaction (Erfidan,2019). In addition, as in the study, the instructors question whether the students who receive distance education learn as much as the students who receive face-to-face education (Balta & Turel, 2013). In the future, it is predicted that distance education will become the primary basis of education or become a secondary learning tool instead of being a support function in face-to-face learning (Telli & Altun, 2020). For these reasons, it is the general opinion that the infrastructure of all relevant units should be improved and supported. In the interviews made with the lecturers, it was seen that the training, support and standardization were emphasized during the preparation of the lessons for the practicing part. For these reasons, it is important suggestions to provide sufficient infrastructure support to the instructors, to provide trainings, to provide expert support while preparing the content, to set standards in terms of methods and techniques to be applied in distance education, and to increase interaction with students (Erfidan, 2019).

When the table titled Data on Courses Given Through the Distance Education Center (23 March-07 April 2020) is examined, the rate of students' use of distance education materials is 50% (Can, 2020). The fact that students have the opportunity to watch the lessons later also reduces synchronous participation and student interest. The fact that students do not use cameras and microphones also causes a loss of motivation for practitioners in terms of the uncertainty of whether the student is in front of them or not (Ozalkan, 2021). Additional problems were encountered due to the fact that some applied courses were completely suitable for the classroom environment (Kurnaz & Sercemeli, 2020). When viewed from the student dimension, students' lack of technological tools and internet problems generally lead to their inability to participate in distance education practices (Marek, Chew & Wu, 2021). Students have self-discipline and self-regulation in this process, they can act responsibly for their own learning, it is important that they be aware of learning and have a self-control mechanism (Durak, et al., 2020).

In addition, the necessary technical / infrastructure of universities should be established in order to evaluate the success of the student. For this reason, measurement and evaluation units for distance education can be established in universities, measurement and evaluation experts can evaluate the questions and situations of the exams and necessary security measures can be taken (Can, 2012). It has also been observed that many of the universities do not have online exam practicing principles, and there is a need for legal regulations for measurement and evaluation in distance education practices (Can, 2020). As a result of the analysis, it was observed that the instructors generally focused on questions such as case studies, case studies, etc. in order to ensure student participation and prevent copying, and they made measurement and evaluation based on the interpretation power of the students on the questions. Bakioglu and Can (2011) mentioned that the same questions are asked over and over again and that the terminology questions cannot measure the success of the students, and that the students can use their metacognitive skills as well (as cited in Can, 2020).

According to the recommendations of UNESCO in terms of planning and applicability of distance education; Encouraging the use of different web tools, the necessity of having a strong internet connection and providing appropriate opportunities for students with device and internet problems, preventing inequality of opportunity in education, finding ways to increase interaction, planning the process by taking into account school closures, making continuous improvements, appropriate learning methods. plan and implement the program according to teachers, students, etc. It has suggested that digital literacy trainings should be given, the use of blended approaches, focusing on the process, making plans for assessment and evaluation and scanning feedback, making and maintaining lesson plans by considering the motivation and interest levels of the students (2020). Higher Education Quality Board (YOKAK, 2020), establishing a distance education policy in a qualified and effective distance education program, increasing technical and infrastructure opportunities, taking into account access situations, usage competencies, education-training processes, expert human resources, support services and information. In this process, there is a need to consider the safety and ethical dimensions.

5. Suggestions

According to the opinions of the instructors, it can be said that distance education programs have not yet achieved the desired efficiency. The following suggestions are given for the elimination of the deficiencies:

- In order to achieve success in distance education, the programs should be arranged in a way that covers the requirements of distance education.
- It is necessary to provide trainings based on serious examples on the design of distance education practices, how to design and conduct the teaching process, and the design and implementation of assessment activities.
- Content development units should be established regarding distance education, and necessary arrangements and improvements should be made by considering the interests and needs of the students, their motivations and the conditions of the social situation.
- A committee can be formed regarding distance education and this committee can make the necessary arrangements. Legal arrangements should be made in terms of the practicality of practices related to distance education.
- Pilot practices related to distance education should be made, legal regulations and laws related to distance education should be prepared in a way that does not leave any gaps.
- To instructors, students. 24/7 technological support regarding distance education should be provided. Support units can be created.
- A general program for distance education should be developed/adapted and revised in line with the feedback received. Regional programs should be put to work.
- Equality of opportunity should be ensured and the necessary technical infrastructure should be established in order for each student to easily access distance education systems, solutions should be developed for the foreseen problems, and possible problems should be predicted and precautions should be taken.

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References

- Akpinar, Y. (2003). Ogretmenlerin Yeni Bilgi Teknolojileri Kullaniminda Yuksekogretim Etkisi: İstanbul Okullari Ornegi [The Effect of Higher Education on Teachers' Use of New Information Technologies: The Example of Istanbul Schools]. *The Turkish Online Journal of Education Technology*, 2(2), 79-96. <http://tojet.net/articles/v2i2/2211.pdf>
- Aydin, C. H. (2020). Uzaktan Egitimin Gelecegine İlişkin Egilimler [Trends in the Future of Distance Education]. 28-36. https://www.emo.org.tr/ekler/7e8f8e5982b3298_ek.pdf?dergi=327
- Bailey, C. J., & Card, K. A. (2009). Effective Pedagogical Practices for Online Teaching: Perception of Experienced Instructors. *Internet and Higher Education*, 12(3-4), 152-155. Doi:10.1016/J.Iheduc.2009.08.002
- Balci, A. (2012). Sosyal Bilimlerde Arastirma (9. Baski) [Research in the Social Sciences (9th Edition)]. Ankara: Pegem A Publishing.
- Balta, Y., & Turel, Y. K. (2013). Cevrimici Uzaktan Egitimde Kullanilan Farkli Olcme Degerlendirme Yaklasimlarina İlişkin Bir Inceleme [A Review of Different Measurement and Evaluation Approaches Used in Online Distance Education]. *Turkish Studies-International Periodical for The Languages, Literature and History of Turkish or Turkic*, 8(3), 37-45. <https://www.acarindex.com/dosyalar/makale/acarindex-1423933010.pdf>
- Baris, M. F., Cankaya, P. (2016). Akademik Personelin Uzaktan Egitim Hakkindaki Gorusleri [Opinions of Academic Staff on Distance Education]. *International Journal of Human Sciences*, 13(1), Ss. 99-413. DOI: 10.14687/ijhs.v13i1.3378
- Bilgic, H., & Tuzun, H. (2015). Yuksekogretim Kurumlari Web Tabanlı Uzaktan Egitim Programlarinda Yasanan Sorunlar [Problems Experienced in Web Based Distance Education Programs of Higher Education Institutions]. *Acikogretim Uygulamalari ve Arastirmalari Dergisi AUAD*. [Journal of Teaching Practices and Research]. 1 (3): 26-50. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/auad/issue/3028/42071>
- Bonk, C. (2001). Online Teaching in an Online World. Http://www.Publicationshare.Com/Docs/Faculty_Survey_Report.Pdf
- Bowers, J., Kumar, P. (2017). Students' Perceptions of Teaching and Social Presence: A Comparative Analysis of Face-To-Face and Online Learning Environments. In Blended Learning: Concepts, Methodologies, Tools, and Applications 1532-1550. IGI Global. DOI:10.4018/ijwltt.2015010103
- Bozkurt, A. (2020). Koronavirus (Covid-19) Pandemi Sureci Ve Pandemi Sonrasi Dunyada Egitime Yonelik Degerlendirmeler: Yeni Normal Ve Yeni Egitim Paradigmasi. [The Coronavirus (Covid-19) Pandemic Process and Post-Pandemic Assessments on Education in the World: The New Normal and New Education Paradigm]. *Auad*, 6(3), 112142. <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/download/article-file/1215818>
- Buyukozturk, S. (2005). Anket gelistirme. [Survey development]. *Turk Egitim Bilimleri Dergisi*, [Turkish Journal of Educational Sciences], 3(2), 133-151. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/tebd/issue/26124/275190>
- Buyukozturk, S. (2012). Sosyal Bilimler İcin Veri Analizi El Kitabı (17. Baski) [Handbook of Data Analysis for the Social Sciences (17th Edition)]. Ankara: PegemA Publishing.
- Buyukozturk, S., Cakmak, K., Akgun, O., Karadeniz, S., & Demirel F. (2008). Bilimsel Arastirma Yontemleri [Scientific Research Methods]. Ankara: Pegem Publishing.
- Can, E. (2012). Acik Ve Uzaktan Egitimde Akreditasyon Yeterlilik Duzeyinin İncelenmesi. [Investigation of Accreditation Sufficiency Level in Open and Distance Education] Marmara University Institute of Educational Sciences, Doctoral Thesis, İstanbul. <https://avesis.marmara.edu.tr/yonetilen-tez/83e22261-2f4c-437e-a4e4-5ae5c76b3de8/acik-ve-uzaktan-egitimde-akreditasyon-yeterlilik-duzeyinin-incelemesi>
- Can, E. (2020). Coronavirus (Covid-19) Pandemisi Ve Pedagogik Yansimalari: Turkiye'de Acik Ve Uzaktan Egitim Uygulamalari. [Coronavirus (Covid-19) Pandemic and Pedagogical Reflections: Open and Distance Education Practices in Turkey.] *Acikogretim Uygulamalari Ve Arastirmalari Dergisi Auad*. [Journal of Teaching Practices and Research]. 6(2), 11-53. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/auad/issue/55662/761354>
- Creswell, J.W. (2007). Qualitative Inquiry & Research Design: Choosing Among Five Approaches. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Cronje, J.C. (2001). Metaphors and models in internet-based learning. *Computers and Education*, 37(3-4), 241-256. <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/92889>
- Deveci, I., & Kavak, S. (2020). Ortaokul Ogrencilerinin Yenilikcilik Algilari ve Yenilikci Dusunme Egilimleri: Bir Kesfedici Ardisik Desen. [Secondary School Students' Perceptions of Innovation and Innovative Thinking Tendencies: An Exploratory Sequential Pattern]. *Egitimde Nitel Arastirmalar Dergisi – [Journal of Qualitative Research in Education]*, 8(1), 346-378. Doi:10.14689/issn.2148-2624.1.8c.1s.15m
- Dooley, K. E. & Murphrey, T. P. (2000). How The Perspectives of Administrators, Faculty, And Support Units Impact The Rate of Distance Education Adoption? *Online Journal of Distance Learning Administration*, 3(4). <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/92503/>

- Durak, G., Cankaya, S., & Izmirli, S. (2020). Covid-19 Pandemi Doneminde Turkiye'deki Universitelerin Uzaktan Egitim Sistemlerinin Incelenmesi. [Examining The Distance Education Systems of Universities in Turkey During the Covid-19 Pandemic Period]. *NEF-EFMED*, 14(1), 787-809. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.17522/balikesirnef.743080>
- Erfidan, A. (2019). Derslerin Uzaktan Egitim Yoluyla Verilmesiyle İlgili Ogretim Elemani Ve Ogrenci Gorusleri: Balikesir Universitesi Ornegi. [The Views of Faculty Members and Students on the Teaching of Courses Through Distance Education: The Example of Balikesir University]. Master Thesis. Balikesir University. <http://dspace.balikesir.edu.tr/xmlui/handle/20.500.12462/5606>
- Falowo, R. O. (2007). Factors Impeding Implementation of Web-Based Distance Learning. *AACE Journal*, 15(3), 315-338. <https://www.learntechlib.org/primary/p/21710>
- Gardner, L. (2020, March 20). Covid-19 Has Forced Higher Ed to Pivot to Online Learning. Here Are 7 Takeaways So Far. *The Chronicle of Higher Education*. <https://www.Chronicle.Com/Article/Covid-19-Has-Forced-Highered/248297>
- Gokmen, O. Duman, İ., & Horzum. M. (2016). Uzaktan Egitimde Kuramlar, Degisimler ve Yeni Yonelimler. [Theories, Changes and New Trends in Distance Education]. *Acikogretim Uygulamalari Ve Arastirmalari Dergisi Auad. [Journal of Teaching Practices and Research]*. 2 (3). 29-51. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/download/article-file/402011>
- Goktas, Y., Yildirim, Z., & Yildirim, S. (2008). Bilgi ve İletisim Teknolojilerinin Egitim Fakultelerindeki Durumu: Dekanlarin Gorusleri. [The Situation of Information and Communication Technologies in Education Faculties: Deans' Opinions]. *Egitim ve Bilim [Education and Science]* 33(149), 30-50. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/44117444_Bilgi_ve_Iletisim_Teknolojilerinin_Egitim_Fakultelerindeki_Durumu_Dekanlarin_Gorusleri
- Green, T., Alejandro, J. & Brown, A. (2009). The Retention of Experienced Faculty In Online Distance Education Programs: Understanding Factors That Impact Their Involvement. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 10(3). <http://www.irrodl.org/index.php/irrodl/article/view/683/1279>
- Gurer, M., Tekinarsan, E., & Yavuzalp, N. (2016). Cevrimici Ders Veren Ogretim Elemanlarinin Uzaktan Egitim Hakkindaki Gorusleri. [Opinions of Instructors Giving Online Courses About Distance Education]. *Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry (TOJQI)*. 7 (1). 47-78 DOI: 10.17569/tojqi.74876
- Isman, A., & Dabaj, F. (2005). Diffusion of Distance Education in North Cyprus. *TOJDE*, 6(4) 1302-6488. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED494755>
- Karahan, M. & Izci, E. (2001). Universite Ogrencilerinin Internet Kullanim Duzeyleri Ve Beklentilerinin Degerlendirilmesi [Evaluation of Internet Usage Levels and Expectations of University Students]. *Milli Egitim Dergisi [Journal of National Education]*. 150. http://yayim.meb.gov.tr/dergiler/150/karahan_izci.html
- Kurnaz, E., & Sercemeli, M. (2020). Covid-19 Pandemi Doneminde Akademisyenlerin Uzaktan Egitim ve Muhasebe Egitimine Yonelik Bakis Acilari Uzerine Bir Arastirma [A Study on the Perspectives of Academics on Distance Education and Accounting Education in the Pandemic Period]. *USBAD Uluslararası Sosyal Bilimler Akademi Dergisi [Journal of the International Academy of Social Sciences]*. 2(3), 262-288. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/download/article-file/1163428>
- Li, X. (2009). Review of Distance Education Used in Higher Education in China. *Asian Journal of Distance Education*, 7(2), 22-27. <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/185183>
- Marek, M. W., Chew, C. S., & Wu, W. V. (2021). Teacher Experiences In Converting Classes to Distance Learning in The Covid-19 Pandemic. *International Journal of Distance Education Technologies*, 19 (1). Doi: 10.4018/Ijdet.20210101.Oa3
- Merriam, S. B. (2009). *Qualitative research: A Guide to Design and Implementation*. Josseybass: Wiley.
- Miles, M. B., Huberman, A. M. (1994). *Qualitative Data Analysis: A Sourcebook of New Methods*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Moore, G., & Anderson, W. (Eds) (2003). *Handbook of Distance Education*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Ozalkan, G. S. (2021). Uzaktan Egitimde Olcme Ve Degerlendirme: Pandemi Surecinde Sosyal Bilimler Egitimini Yeniden Dusunmek. [Assessment and Evaluation in Distance Education: Rethinking Social Science Education in the Pandemic Process]. *IJEASS*. (4), 18-26. <http://ijeass.gedik.edu.tr/tr/download/article-file/1547485>
- Ozer, M. (2020). Covid-19 Salgini Sonrasi Dunyada Egitim. [Education in the World After the Covid-19 Pandemic]. <https://www.meb.gov.tr/covid-19-salgini-sonrasi-dunyadaegitim/haber/20936/tr>
- Ozgol, M., Sarikaya, İ. & Ozturk, M. (2017). Orgun Egitimde Uzaktan Egitim Uygulamalarina Iliskin Ogrenci Ve Ogretim Elemani Degerlendirmeleri [Student and Instructor' Evaluations On Distance Education Practices in Formal Education]. *Yuksekogretim Ve Bilim Dergisi [Journal of Higher Education and Science]* (2), 294-304. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/higheredusci/issue/61493/918176>

- Petzold, A. M. (2020). Letter to The Editor: Resources and Recommendations for A Quick Transition to Online Instruction in Physiology. *Advances in Physiology Education*, 44, 217-219. Doi:10.1152/Advan.00049.2020
- Saritas, E., & Barutcu, S. (2020). Ogretimde Dijital Donusum ve Ogrencilerin Cevrimici Ogrenmeye Hazir Bulunuslulugu: Pandemi Doneminde Pamukkale Universitesi Ogrencileri Uzerinde Bir Arastirma [Digital Transformation in Education and Students' Readiness for Online Learning: A Study on Pamukkale University Students during the Pandemic Period]. *IUYD*, 11(1), 5-22. <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/download/article-file/1124968>
- Sayan, H. (2020). Covid-19 Pandemisi Surecinde Ogretim Elemanlarinin Uzaktan Egitime İlişkin Goruslerinin Degerlendirilmesi. [Evaluation of Instructors Views on Distance Education during the Covid-19 Pandemic Process]. *AJIT-e: Bilisim Teknolojileri Online Dergisi [Information Technologies Online Journal]* 11 (42). <https://doi.org/10.5824/ajite.2020.03.004.x>
- Telli, S. G., & Altun, D. (2020). Coronavirus ve Cevrimici (Online) Egitimin Onlenemeyen Yukselisi [Coronavirus and the Unstoppable Rise of Online Education]. *Universite Arastirmalari Dergisi [Journal of University Studies]* 3(1), 25-34. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.32329/uad.711110>
- Tuncer, M., & Tanas, R. (2011). Akademisyenlerin Uzaktan Egitim Programlarına Yonelik Goruslerinin Degerlendirilmesi (Firat Ve Tunceli Universiteleri Ornegi) [Evaluation of Academicians' Opinions on Distance Education Programs (Firat and Tunceli Universities Example)]. *Ilkogretim Online [Primary Education Online]* 10 (2), 776- 784. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/ilkonline/issue/8592/106837>
- Ulmer, L. W., Watson, L. W. & Derby, D. (2007). Perceptions of higher education faculty members on the value of distance education. *Quarterly Review of Distance Education*, 8, 59-70. https://www.academia.edu/65137635/Perceptions_of_Higher_Education_Faculty_Members_on_the_Value_of_Distance_Education
- UNESCO. (2020). COVID-19: 10 Recommendations to Plan Distance Learning Solutions. <https://en.unesco.org/news/covid-19-10-recommendations-plan-distance-learning-solutions>.
- Yildirim, A., & Simsek, H. (2013). Sosyal Bilimlerde Nitel Arastirma Yontemleri [Qualitative research methods in the social sciences]. Seckin Publishing.
- YOKAK. (2020). Yuksekogretimde Uzaktan Egitim Ve Kalite Guvencesi Sistemi [Distance Education and Quality Assurance System in Higher Education]. <https://portal.yokak.gov.tr/makale/uzaktan-egitim-ve-kalite-guvence-sistemi/>
- Zan, N., & Zan, B. U. (2020). Koronavirus İle Acil Durumda Egitim: Turkiye'nin Farkli Bolgelerinden Uzaktan Egitim Sistemine Dahil Olan Edebiyat Fakultesi Ogrencilerine Genel Bakis [Education in an Emergency with the Coronavirus: An Overview of the Faculty of Letters Students Included in the Distance Education System from Different Regions of Turkey]. *Turkish Studies*, 15(4), 1367-1394. DOI: 10.7827/TurkishStudies.44365